
A storybook presenting the Art of Thinking

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[Book Review]

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★★★★★ Verified Purchase

An Art of Thinking book from the modern life stories

Reviewed in the United States on September 24, 2024

Like other books of Dr. Vuong, I always had a good laugh and intellectually stimulating time after reading his book.

As someone who has experienced the frustrations of government procedures, the "culture" of doing research, or the poor and crowded streets in Vietnam, I found Dr. Vuong's observation both hilarious and poignant. This ability to tackle these everyday annoyances with humor and turn them into opportunities for reflection is truly masterful.

Screenshot. Reviewed in the United States on September 24, 2024 [1]

Like other books of Dr. Vuong, I always had a good laugh and an intellectually stimulating time after reading his book [2].

As someone who has experienced the frustrations of government procedures, the “culture” of doing research, or the poor and crowded streets in Vietnam, I found Dr. Vuong’s observation both hilarious and poignant. This ability to tackle these everyday annoyances with humor and turn them into opportunities for reflection is truly masterful.

The traffic jam stories particularly struck me, bringing back my college days in Vietnam’s busy roads. Dr. Vuong’s clever anecdotes about these situations not only made me laugh but also gave me a pause for critical self-reflection—to think more deeply about the ironies and paradoxes in my daily life.

Even though the book’s structure might not be familiar to a traditional narrative reader, it’s perfect for anyone who enjoys bite-sized wisdom and can be read sporadically. Considering its modest price, the book is a worthy reading for anyone who wants to develop critical thinking and want to explore the world through a more nuanced lens for growth and understanding.

(*) *Note:* Tran Thi Mai Anh is a doctoral scholar at the College of Forest Resources and Environmental Science, Michigan Technological University, Houghton, MI 49931 USA. This column reprints Mai Anh’s review appearing on the Amazon page of the title: <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R1M2POZIVRKE08>, with some light edits for clarity and fitting our house style.

References

[1] Anh TTM. (2024). An Art of Thinking book from the modern life stories. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R1M2POZIVRKE08>

[2] Vuong QH. (2023). *Meandering Sobriety*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOC2TXNX6L>

